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The relationship between public health and profitability in food sector

KEYWORDS

health status,
food business
profitability,
cubic parabola,
health
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The connection between population health and profitability in the food sector is relevant because a healthy population can drive demand for quality products, while business development can contribute to improved nutrition and public health.

This study is aimed at developing theoretical provisions for the dependence of the general integrated health status of the population on the total aggregate profitability indicator of the food business.

Materials and methods. The materials used in the study were as follows: scientific publications and research in nutrition, public health, economics, and marketing addressing the relationship between population health and profitability in the food sector. Methods employed in the study included modeling and forecasting to develop scenarios for the food sector, taking into account population health status.

Results. A theoretical dependence of the integral health indicator on the overall aggregate profitability rate of the agro-industrial complex, food industry, and food retail has been established. Variations in health status under different parameters of its parabolic dependence on the aggregate profitability of the food business were examined. A conditional numerical example of the dependence in the form of a cubic parabola of health status on changes in the total aggregate profitability rate of the food business was presented and analyzed. It was concluded that the primary task of establishing and achieving health status indicators (the overarching goal) involved not only market-driven but also state-regulated provision of appropriate parameters for the overall aggregate profitability of the food business. It was proven that an increase in profitability (return on sales) of food products affected changes in population health, particularly in terms of nutritional disorders and metabolic dysfunctions.

Conclusion. Growing public awareness of proper nutrition encourages companies to develop and promote healthier products, such as organic and functional foods. This helps optimize production by reducing costs and strengthens marketing strategies through collaboration with medical and governmental organizations. As a result, demand for healthier products increases, contributing to reduced healthcare costs and the creation of new jobs in the healthy food sector and related industries.

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INTRODUCTION

Within the framework of food security, ensuring the alignment of economic interests between food producers and population health status is of critical importance in the process of food consumption. The economic interests of food producers and sellers are maximizing profits from food sales. The interests of the population include maintaining and improving health through the consumption of high-quality food products, as well as preserving the ecological conditions of their habitats. Coordination of these interests is a complex scientific and applied challenge that is addressed daily across all food production and retail markets.

Thus, in modern society, an increasing number of consumers are paying attention to the quality and composition of the products they consume. Food companies that recognize these trends and offer healthier products can attract more customers and increase their profitability. New regulations and standards aimed at improving food quality and safety can also influence production processes, packaging, labeling, and other aspects of food industry operations. However, investments in healthy nutrition may lead to reduced healthcare costs and increased labor productivity, which could positively impact the national economy and the profitability of food sector companies.

Modern technologies enable the development of new food products enriched with vitamins, minerals, and other beneficial nutrients. This creates new opportunities for companies seeking to offer consumers high-quality and health-promoting food products.

The study is aimed at analyzing the relationship between the increase in profitability (return on sales) of food products and changes in population health status, particularly in terms of nutritional disorders and metabolic dysfunctions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials included scientific publications and studies in the fields of nutrition, public health, economics, and marketing focusing on the relationship between population health and profitability in the food sector (Discover Sustainability; Environment, Development and Sustainability; Economic Change and Restructuring; The Annals of Regional Science; Canadian Studies in Population; Research in Health Services & Regions; Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health; Nature Food; Global Health; Agriculture and Food Security).

The methods employed were modeling and forecasting to develop future scenarios for the food sector, taking into account population health status.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic growth contributes to improved population health status through increased incomes, better living conditions, expanded access to healthcare services, and enhanced nutrition. However, rapid growth may exacerbate social inequality and environmental degradation, potentially adversely affecting health. Overall, stable economic growth promotes increased life expectancy and reduced morbidity.

M. E. Cerf et al. emphasize that sustainable development requires well-educated individuals who contribute to economic growth while having access to quality healthcare [1].

X. Yan et al. employed panel structural vector autoregression to analyze the interrelationships between environmental quality, economic growth, and health status in China's Yellow River Basin. Their findings indicate that expanding economic growth harms the environment. Increased healthcare expenditures also negatively impact both the economy and the environment. However, environmental quality was not identified as a contributing factor to economic development and public health at the current stage [2].

J. Zhao et al. investigate the impact of economic growth on public health in Western China. According to the research, economic growth reduces mortality rates. Advances in technological progress and healthcare services significantly improve public health outcomes [3].

Y. Fan et al. reach similar conclusions, stating that economic growth correlates with lower public health vulnerability, whereas urbanization exerts adverse effects on public health [4].

A. C. Patterson argues that while economic growth may enhance health in certain contexts, for specific countries, and when combined with other livelihood priorities, it does not inherently improve population health in isolation [5].

N. Kontodimopoulos highlights the contradictions in the literature on the relationship between socio-economic development and health, examining how this relationship may vary across countries with differing economic growth levels.

The author demonstrates that higher economic development levels showed stronger correlations with health in wealthier nations, while lower levels were more significant in poorer countries [6].

M. Hu et al. analyze the role of air quality (greenhouse gas, carbon, and nitrogen emissions), forest coverage, healthcare expenditures, and socio-economic conditions in the growth of health problems in China. Income inequality and socio-economic conditions also contributed significantly to health-related issues [7].

The above studies reveal interconnections between economic development, environmental conditions, and public health. The impact of economic development on health depends on a country's wealth level and socio-economic conditions, while environmental quality and income inequality also play crucial roles in shaping societal health.

Population health status directly depends on nutrition: balanced and adequate nutrition strengthens immunity, reduces disease risks, and enhances quality of life, whereas poor nutrition leads to chronic diseases and health deterioration.

A. Yadav argues that the interconnection between nutrition and other scientific disciplines has given rise to a new field of interdisciplinary research integrating concepts from agriculture, nutrition, economics, and social sciences [8].

R. Ambikapathi et al. study the dynamics of food systems: from rural and traditional to industrial and consolidated. According to the authors, food systems of all types fail to deliver optimal outcomes in nutrition and health, environmental sustainability, as well as inclusivity and equality for all [9].

K. Afsana et al. present the current nutrition and food safety scenario, highlighting how it overlaps with essential health issues, including morbidity and mortality trends, as well as social determinants of health [10].

Z. Kubik et al. propose a conceptual framework that shows the complex interactions between climate change, food systems, and food and nutrition security. In particular, the authors believe that the adverse impacts of climate change on food and nutrition security have significant consequences for human capital accumulation and labor market outcomes [11].

S. Phulkerd et al. note that the core "problem" presented in Thailand's food investment policy was the perceived irrelevance of nutrition to government commitments to improve productivity and economic growth. The authors highlight that technological innovations in food production and processing, such as the

development of ultra-processed foods, were perceived as a key driver of economic growth. The research results indicate that nutrition was not perceived as a political priority for the government and other investment entities [12].

T. Kızıldeniz et al. note that in many underdeveloped and developing countries, providing people with safe and nutritious food remains a significant challenge. The authors propose a climate-smart approach to agriculture that aims to reorient and change agricultural systems to effectively enhance progress and ensure food security under changing climatic conditions [13].

H. Walls et al. consider the impact of Malawi's (Africa) Farm Input Subsidy Program on overall food choices. According to the authors, maize-focused programs may increase maize production and consumption but reduce the intake of nutrient-rich foods [14].

One of the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals is to end hunger, ensure food security, and improve nutrition by 2030. In 2021, approximately 821 million people suffered from chronic undernourishment, with even more at risk.

T. K. Meyer et al. demonstrate that even a modest increase in taxes on tobacco, alcohol, or firearms sales within the United States alone could address the caloric needs of people in areas with high food insecurity. The authors conclude that reallocating funds from products harmful to the U.S. population represents a pathway toward achieving global food security and sustainable food production [15].

M. Mwambi et al. highlight that the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted global food security; however, the analyses of its effects on the cost and availability of healthy diets remain limited. The authors demonstrate that the primary impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the availability of healthy food was due to lower incomes among people experiencing poverty, rather than price increases [16].

E. B. Dompok et al. emphasize that small-scale aquaculture constitutes a critical food source in Myanmar, yet farmers face limited access to advanced production technologies and information. The authors argue that sustained support for small-scale producers should be incorporated into development initiatives and projects aimed at enhancing food security and rural development [17].

H. Temesgen and C. S. Aweke examined the impact of smallholder agricultural production on food and nutrition security in Ethiopia. The results of the review showed that smallholder farmers play a critical role in efforts to improve food and nutrition

security, either directly as food sources or indirectly by providing the means and mechanisms to access the right type of food at different levels [18].

According to E. B. Ntiamoah et al., long-term food security in East Africa benefits from economic expansion, population growth, trade openness, and agricultural employment [19].

Research by R. Osabohien has demonstrated that green economy development enhances food security levels across Africa [20].

This review emphasizes the importance of integrating ideas from agriculture, economics, and the social sciences to address global challenges, including nutrition provision, environmental sustainability, and social equality. Various factors affecting food systems are considered: climate change, technological innovations, investment and subsidy policies, and the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

RESULTS

The logic of the dependence between the general health status of the population and the total profit margin of food production and sales can be broadly represented as an ascending and then descending parabolic curve (see Fig. 1), which reaches an optimal static value at the inflection point **B** (the vertex of the parabola). The downward trajectory of the right branch of the parabola is explained by Karl Marx's famous statement in his work [21]: "Secure 10%, and capital agrees to every application, at 20% it becomes lively, at 50% it is positively ready to break its head, at 100% it violates all human laws, at 300% there is no crime it would not risk, even under the threat of the gallows". Thus, the higher the profit margin pursued by businesses, the less food producers (now predominantly private capital) will prioritize consumer health.

Prio to the inflection point **B**, the improvement in health status is driven by an increase in the aggregate profit margin, which is stimulated through various forms of state and corporate regulation aimed at enhancing the economic performance of enterprises producing quality food products. This is intended to increase life expectancy, preserve health, and improve environmental conditions. The achievement of maximum health status (point **A**) corresponds to the static optimal coordinated value of the aggregate profit margin for agribusiness, food industry, and food retail enterprises (point **C**).

Figure 1 The relationship between health status and the aggregate profit margin of agribusiness, food industry, and food retail

Source: Developed by the authors

Point **B** (the vertex of the parabola), which results from the overarching goal of achieving the required level of robust population health (Point **A**), should be considered the target benchmark for the aggregate profit margin of agribusiness, food industry, and food retail enterprises (Point **C**). The trajectory along points **A-B-C**, based on the fundamental objective of attaining optimal population health, establishes the foundational parameter for determining the aggregate profit margin in these sectors (Point **C**). Any further increase in the aggregate profit margin beyond this point leads to deterioration in population health through food consumption.

After reaching peak health status, additional growth in the aggregate profit margin can only be achieved by compromising food quality and safety through cost-cutting measures in production being practices that benefit businesses but harm public health and must be regulated by authorities. Notably, intermediate health levels (Points **D** and **G**) may occur under both moderate and maximum profit margin conditions. When comparing equal health status levels between Points **F** and **G**, the corresponding aggregate profit margin is substantially higher at Point **H** (parameter **H** significantly exceeds parameter **E**), demonstrating the nonlinear relationship between profitability and health outcomes. Minor health deteriorations enable disproportionate profit increases, frequently incentivizing unethical practices like selling expired or hazardous food products.

The right-side area of the curve (beyond optimal health levels) represents an illegal operational zone where the logical dependence between health status and profit margins must be strictly prohibited through government oversight. Specialized regulatory and law enforcement institutions exist precisely to monitor this prohibited zone (the entire area under this curve segment is marked negative). Profit margins falling within this range for agribusiness, food production, and retail enterprises constitute a forbidden territory that actively degrades national health indicators. Any business attempts to increase profitability within this prohibited zone must be recognized as unlawful and suppressed to safeguard public health in food consumption.

Particular attention should be paid to point **F** on the parabolic curve in question. This point is determined by the tangent of a 45-degree line to the graph axes. It represents an equilibrium where the growth rates of both health status and aggregate profit from food production and sales are equal. Above this point, health improvements grow slower than profit increases; below it, health gains outpace profit growth. This point serves as a dynamic optimum balancing business interests (agribusiness, food industry, and retail) with health outcomes. However, the overarching goal of improving population health demands reaching its static optimal value (point **A**). Movement along the parabola from point **D** to point **A** requires profit growth to exceed health improvement rates, demonstrating the substantial cost of achieving robust health and necessitating careful regulation of economic processes affecting nutritional safety. This scenario represents the most desirable state within a country's socio-economic system, where public health interests align with business processes producing quality food (the area under the curve before intersection with the line between points **D** and **G** is marked positive).

Any deviation from point **B** on the graph under consideration should trigger corrective measures by both authorities and businesses to restore optimal static conditions in food production and distribution – those ensuring target health outcomes (point **A**) through food consumption.

A significant challenge in analyzing and predicting the relationship between the state of health of the population and the total rate of profit of food producers is coordinating the interests of individual producers and suppliers within a consistent food production chain. The leading players in the food market, including the agro-industrial complex, the fishing industry, the food industry, transportation, trade, and public catering, have their own profit-making interests, which are coordinated by the food circulation and sales market. The aggregate profit margin across this

sequential chain should maintain normative parameters as generalized in Figure 1. Market-based price coordination (and consequently profit distribution) with potential government intervention constitutes a distinct task within the framework of achieving target population health benchmarks.

Health status improvements can be achieved by shifting the parabolic dependence on aggregate profit margins toward enhanced comprehensive performance of studied parameters (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 The relationship between health status and the aggregate profit margin of agribusiness, food industry, and food retail under parabolic shift conditions

Source: Developed by the authors.

Compared to the parameters of Figure 1, the trajectory from target health status to aggregate profit margin shifts from **A-B-C** to **A¹-B¹-C¹** in Figure 2. The second trajectory, enabling higher health parameters and greater aggregate profit margins for food businesses, represents the preferable model for organizing and regulating population health maintenance systems.

It should be noted that point **B** (the vertex of the first parabola) in our example coincides with the intersection of optimal health status and the left branch of the second parabola. The left branch of the second parabola prevents health deterioration despite increasing profit margins in the food business – a phenomenon not observed when analyzing the first parabola's dependencies. This demonstrates the feasibility of simultaneously improving health indicators (from point **A** to **A¹**) while

increasing aggregate profit margins (from point **C** to **C¹**), justifying the creation of conditions for rightward parabolic shift with upward vertex displacement. This corresponds to concurrent growth in both profitability and health outcomes.

Further examination of health status dependence on agribusiness, food industry, and retail profit margins can be extended through triple parabolic displacement analysis (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3 The relationship between health status and the aggregate profit margin of agribusiness, food industry, and food retail under double parabolic displacement conditions

Source: Developed by the authors

The proposed third configuration of parameter relationships demonstrates new, higher benchmarks at points **A²-B²-C²** and their interconnections. Notably, the left branch of the third parabola intersects with the descending right branch of the second parabola (point **D**) and the right branch of the first parabola (point **E**), indicating potential real-world scenarios where health deterioration may be interrupted despite increasing food sector profitability. This phenomenon reveals diverse possibilities for managing population health within the complex dependency on aggregate profit margins across agribusiness, food processing, and retail sectors.

The upward linear displacement of the parabolic vertex represents the desirable trajectory of simultaneous health improvement and food business profit growth. In practical applications, this displacement may follow more complex non-linear paths

without altering the fundamental objective: enhancing population health indicators while harmonizing food business objectives.

In the initial model, the downward-oriented parabolic branches logically explained two phases: left-side health improvement during profit margin growth, and right-side health deterioration with further profit increases. The second scenario's upward-oriented parabolic branches invert this relationship, demonstrating continued health improvement alongside rising profitability when both left and right branches maintain convex orientation. This economic logic suggests sustainable co-development of health outcomes and business performance when the system achieves optimal configuration.

Figure 4 The relationship between health status and the aggregate profit margin of agribusiness, food industry, and food retail under conditions of convexity change in the right parabolic branch

Source: Developed by the authors

For authorities and businesses, it is necessary to establish conditions enabling the transition from point **F** to point **E** while maintaining the same aggregate profit margin in the food sector. In Figure 4, this transition is marked by an upward arrow and a plus sign. The objective of improving health status (the overarching goal) should be supported by appropriate economic incentives for food businesses (budgetary subsidies, preferential taxation, facilitated credit conditions, etc.). This serves as a “carrot” in the system of economic relations. The theoretical form of this dependency, with the right branch redirected upward, takes the shape of a cubic parabola.

A critical factor in fundamentally altering the right branch's trajectory upward (instead of downward) amid profit growth is the strengthening of sanctions against producers and sellers of low-quality and health-hazardous food products. Sanction regimes and punitive measures should escalate in severity proportionally to the harm inflicted on consumers by substandard or harmful food products. This framework for trade relations acts as a "whip" for food producers, who must bear responsibility (including criminal liability) for potential health damage caused by their products.

Such theoretical conditions as transitioning from the parabolic vertex (where no further health improvement occurs) to continued health gains alongside rising aggregate food sector profits align with the interests of both the population and food producers. However, this state, given the typically divergent dynamics of the incremental variables under study, may necessitate further government regulation to ensure unconditional growth in the integral parameter of population health status, ultimately achieving its strategic target value.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The synthesis of theoretical principles regarding the dependence of the general integrated health status of the population on the aggregate profit indicator of the food business has revealed a logical relationship between these parameters.

As awareness of the importance of a healthy lifestyle and proper nutrition grows, companies can develop and promote products that improve consumer health. This may include the production of organic products, functional products with added nutritional value, and products free from harmful additives.

Understanding the relationship between population health and profitability can help companies optimize their manufacturing processes to produce healthier products more efficiently and at lower costs.

Companies can develop marketing strategies that emphasize the health benefits of their products for consumers. This may include collaboration with medical and scientific institutions to validate product benefits.

Companies can collaborate with government agencies and international organizations to develop and implement food quality and safety standards, as well as conduct educational campaigns promoting healthy nutrition.

Research in this area can enhance consumer awareness of the importance of healthy eating and the impact of dietary habits on health. This, in turn, can stimulate demand for healthier products.

Health-promoting products can help reduce the cost of treating diseases associated with a poor diet. This can lead to economic benefits for both individuals and society as a whole.

Companies can develop innovative packaging and logistics solutions to ensure the freshness and quality of products, which in turn contribute to better health.

The growth of the healthy nutrition sector can create new jobs in production, marketing, research and development, while also fostering the development of related industries such as organic agriculture.

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